

MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation.

Every few years, new foreign language teaching methods arrive on the scene. New textbooks appear far more frequently on the bases of new pedagogical technologies with taking into consideration the use of didactic material, pictures, videos, role plays and other teaching techniques. It is believed that information about findings and theoretical views in second language acquisition research can make you a better judge of claims made by textbook writers and proponents of various language teaching methods, techniques and aids. Such information, combined with insights gained from your experience as a language teacher or learner, can help you evaluate proposed changes in classroom methodology.

Key words: teaching methods, pedagogical technologies, didactic material, acquisition.

Development of material

In recent years a number of publications have focused on how materials developers typically write ELT materials. For example, both Hidalgo, Hall and Jacobs (1995) and Prowse (1998) asked numerous authors to detail their typical procedures; Bell and Gower (1998) reflected on their own procedures for writing a course book; Johnson (2003) gave expert writers a material development task and researched the procedures they used; and Tomlinson (2003) reviewed the literature on writing ELT materials. This literature reveals that many experienced writers rely on their intuitions about what "works" and make frequent use of activities from their repertoire that seem to fit with their objectives. Not many writers seem to be actually guided by a prior articulation of learning principles.

The literature does, however, provide some examples of writers who develop materials from a set of principles. For example, in Hidalgo et al. (1995) there are a number of writers who articulate principled approaches to materials development, especially Hall (1995, 8), who insists that we start by asking the crucial question, "How do we think people learn languages?" Bell and Gower (1998) articulate principles to help authors make compromises to meet the practical needs of teachers and learners and to match the realities of publishing materials; Maley (1998) makes suggestions for "providing greater flexibility in decisions about content, order, pace and procedures" (p. 280); Jolly and Bolitho

(1998) advocate a principled framework that involves identification, realization, use, evaluation, and revision; and Tomlinson (1998b) proposes 15 principles for materials development that derive from his second-language acquisition research and experience. As well as reporting on recommended procedures for materials development, McGrath (2002, 152-161) reviews the literature on principled frameworks and he focuses on the theme or topic-based approach, the text-based approach, and the story-line approach. Tomlinson (2003a) contains, for example, chapters on a principled process of materials evaluation that involves turning beliefs into universal principles and profiles into local criteria (Tomlinson 2003b), a principled process for writing a course book (Mares 2003), ways of developing principled frameworks for producing materials (Tomlinson 2003c), creative approaches to writing materials (Maley 2003), and ways of humanizing the course book (i.e., making it of more personal relevance and value to the human beings using it) (Tomlinson 2003d). And Tomlinson (2008b) contains an introductory chapter - "Language Acquisition and Language Learning Materials" - that proposes ways of applying commonly agreed theories of language acquisition to materials development. As yet there is still very little literature reporting research results of projects investigating the actual effectiveness of language learning materials. However, Tomlinson and Masuhara (2010) publish the results of research projects from around the world that are attempting to discover how effective certain types of materials are in the learning contexts in which they are being used. You could argue that the repertoire approach of using again what worked previously makes a lot of sense. But what does "worked" mean? Often it means that the learners enjoyed using the material or that it was easy enough for them to get good marks. But very rarely does "it worked" mean it facilitated language learning. Also, every target group is different and needs materials to be specially developed for it. My position, therefore, is that materials should not be random recreations from repertoire nor clones of previously successful materials. Instead they should be coherent and principled applications of theories of language acquisition and of what is known about the target context of learning. Writers need to articulate their beliefs about how languages are best acquired and to convert them into universal criteria for the development and evaluation of their materials. These criteria will be relevant for every set of materials that the writers develop. They also need to develop local criteria from their knowledge of the characteristics of the target learning context for a particular set of materials.

These criteria should be used in conjunction with universal criteria but will only be relevant for one specific set of materials.

Here are some examples of the universal criteria I use when developing materials:

1. Learners should be exposed to a rich, meaningful, and comprehensible input of language in use.
2. In order for the learners to maximize their exposure to language in use they need to be engaged both affectively and cognitively in the language experience.
3. Learners who achieve positive affect are much more likely to achieve communicative competence than those who do not.
4. L2 language learners can benefit from using those mental resources that they typically utilize when acquiring and using their L1.
5. Language learners can benefit from noticing salient features of their input.
6. Learners need opportunities to use language to try to achieve communicative purposes.

MATERIALS for LEARNING or ACQUISITION

Learning-focused materials provide learners with deliberate and explicit teaching of discrete target features of the language. Acquisition-focused materials provide learners with such language experiences as reading stories, performing plays, and completing tasks in order to help them acquire language from comprehensible input and motivated use. Proponents of a focus on acquisition (e.g., Tomlinson 2008b) argue that affective and cognitive engagement while experiencing language in use is the key to effective language acquisition, but most course books continue to cater for a perceived need for systematic presentation of discrete learning points (Tomlinson et al. 2001; Masuhara et al. 2008). The answer, in my view, is to design textbooks so that they provide learners with engaging language experiences but also ask them to reflect on those experiences and to analyze them in order to make discoveries about language use.

SHOULD MATERIALS BE SAFE OR PROVOCATIVE?

Commercial publishers understandably play safe when publishing global course books. They make sure that they avoid texts, photos, and activities that might cause offence, disturbance or embarrassment. In doing so they make sure that the institutions and the teachers who use their materials are safe from accusation and that they themselves are safe from prosecution. Unfortunately though, this caution often leads to the publication of books that are sanitized, bland, and boring, in which harmony, cooperation, and agreement prevail, and in

which the learners are insulted by the portrayal of an unreal EFL world where fear, danger, sickness, satire, conflict, criticism, disagreement, and even apprehension do not exist. This means that the learners can spend an entire semester not laughing, not being moved, not thinking, and not being stimulated at all. In my experience, ministries of education are often flexible and open-minded when approached for permission to include provocative texts in local course books. In Namibia, for example, we got permission to include in our secondary school textbook texts relating to marital violence, to the supernatural, to the dangers of tourism, and to drug abuse - topics not normally found in global course books. The result was that the students appreciated being asked to think about realities in their world and the textbook was very popular.

SELECTING DIDACTIC MATERIAL

When teaching correct pronunciation, the effective method was to show the articulation of sounds. In addition to that, we used images of English sound articulation. Then we introduced the articulation of Uzbek sound. We compared and contrasted difficult Uzbek sounds with each other and with the sounds of the English language. The habit of observing the articulation of sounds, comparing and contrasting the work of the speech organs produced good results. The selection of educational material on phonetics was presented both empirically and through the introduction of terms: the sound of speech, letter, vowel, consonant, syllable, stress, unstressed, voiceless, voiced, hard, soft, fricative: at the first stage of study, didactic material related to the reduction of unstressed vowels, with rules of voicing and devoicing, was presented empirically, at the second stage of study, comparing articulations of sounds and positional sounds, modulating the timbre of Uzbek speech. The lexical material should be selected due to the possibility of understanding the lexical meanings of words not only as a dictionary unit, but also in a certain context. Taking into account the matter of the language, the principle of understanding linguistic meanings, the principle of speech expressiveness, the principle of developing a sense of language, giving primary importance to the development of oral speech and the communicative principle, observing general didactic principles when selecting didactic materials, one can achieve certain success in teaching foreign students. Speech material was aimed at distinguishing speech material was aimed at distinguishing between strong and weak positions. And since the positional changes of sounds allow us to establish the morphological criterion, the same morpheme was present in the material, but in different speech talk spurts. If native speakers pronounce the stressed and unstressed syllables intuitively,

then foreigners need to develop ability to feel the stress in the word with the help of exercises in which the difference in the pronunciation of stressed and unstressed syllables is obvious. At the third stage of training, the focus was on developing the elements of intonation. Conducting was used to develop speech tempo. After threetime choral reading under the guidance of a teacher, one of the students conducted the study. Texts were read very slowly, slowly, at an average pace, quickly, very quickly. Such work was carried out throughout the year. Voice strength was developed on the basis of imitative exercises. To develop the skills of expressive reading, we suggested watching cartoons and listening to tape recordings. Ways to explain the word meaning were use of visual aids, the selection of synonyms, translation. The definitions that we used to explain the terms were taken from textbooks for elementary school. For example, synonyms are words that mean the same thing, but in different ways. Synonymous lines were given in three styles (neutral, book, and conversational). A set of new vocabulary and its revision took place purposefully also in the classes of other teachers and spontaneously in extracurricular activities, during cultural events, in everyday situations. At the initial stage of training, we took monosemantic words that were not stylistically marked. Monosemantic words were combined on the themes "Furniture", "Household Appliances", "Flowers", "Trees", "Berries", "Mushrooms", "Fruits", "Vegetables", "Animals of Africa", "Animals of the North", "Birds", "Pets", "Wild animals", "Dishes", "Food", "Clothing", "Shoes", "Shop", "Hospital", "Summer", "Winter", "Spring", "Autumn", "Time", "Man", "Nationality", "Color", "Insects". When working, we took into account that the synonymous possibilities of monosemantic words of different lexical sets are not the same that is connected with the logical and subject content of these words. Visibility principle caused a specific image which facilitated to memorize words. The word is not only a lexical, but also a morphological unit, it is a part of speech that has grammatical forms. Mastering the grammatical forms of the Uzbek language for English-speaking foreigners presents great difficulties. In English there are almost no changes in cases and no grammatical category of the genus. In English it is enough to add S in order to put a noun in the plural. Any grammatical form can be understood only by relating it to the phenomena of extralinguistic reality. When working at the meaning of prefixes and suffixes, we used, first, separate words, then texts illustrating their use. We represented grammatical forms in texts. A specific word with a specific lexical meaning becomes a component of a sentence, takes a syntactic position and detects a combination of links. We worked at the

phenomena of a logical series without introducing terminology: the students assimilated the forms for designating predicative relations, assimilated the relations of place, time, cause, object, attribute, person and ways of expressing them. A sufficiently large part of the material for mastering grammatical relations was illustrated texts which made it possible to understand the meaning of functional words. Students could keep up a conversation on every day, cultural, professional, and socio-political topics at a pace that is common to colloquial speech. The presentation of didactic material in the form of didactic games allowed to increase the level of communicative skills formation, to become more relaxed in communication. One of the conditions for the development of a student's speech and communication skills in a class was to create an atmosphere of trust and openness in the audience. We would call it adhering to the principle of psychological comfort. It is difficult to achieve the final result without creating a friendly atmosphere and cooperation with students. We shared the experience of selecting one of the main teaching tools - didactic material - in this article. We selected didactic material paying attention to the language substance, following the principle of linguistic meaning understanding, implementing the principle of evaluating speech expressiveness, the principle of developing a sense of language, giving primary importance to the development of oral speech, relying on the communicative principle, respecting common didactic principles, notably principle of systematicity (systematic approach to training), the principle of consciousness and activity, visibility, accessibility, gradual increase in requirements, thus we were able to achieve some success in teaching foreign students. To achieve it, we also used the principles of activity, continuity, variability, creativity and the creation of psychological comfort.

Visual aids

Using visual aids can help learners understand the deep meaning of a topic and realize similarities and differences between each topic. In learning foreign language using visual aids is a main teaching strategy. We know that memorizing language forms and words is a difficult process. In ELT classroom using visual aids can help students to strengthen and reinforce what they have learnt. The reason may be that they allow students to absorb the information through an additional sensory perception.

If teachers use visual aids regularly, students will expect to learn the next language topic by using visual aids, because each visual aid for them is an interesting learning tool. Facilitating an interesting learning environment can

enhance students' English abilities and this is a major goal for English teachers. These aids allow students to have a chance to brainstorm and present their ideas or thoughts. They can create their own stories in which there are no right or wrong answers. Furthermore, they can also participate in group work such as paired reading or small group activity. They will have the opportunities to create their own stories that depend on their background experience. In group work they can discuss the similarities and the differences between each person's interpretation of a picture. Visual aids help teachers' presentations and objectives by placing emphasis on whatever is being thought. Clear visual aids multiply learners' level of understanding of the material presented, and they can send clear messages and clarify points from teachers. Moreover, they can involve the audience by providing a change from one activity to another, and from hearing to seeing. In addition, learners are more fascinated by gestures and movements in the classroom. Also visual aids impact and add interest to a presentation. They can create excitement. Visual aids enable learners to use more than one sense at the same time. One picture could elicit unlimited words. As for me, in my lessons I try to use various visual aids. Graphic organizers is a very effective in our lessons. Students are always involved doing Cluster, Vienna Diagram, classification chart, T scheme and others. As I teach medical students most of our topics are connected with medicine. So if the topic is Skeleton I suggest students to make Cluster according the topic. If our topics are diseases, for example, Alimentary tract diseases, students can create Vienna diagram.

Vienna diagram

On the first circle students write peculiarities of gastric ulcer (symptoms, clinic manifestations etc), on the other they write these features of chronic gastritis. In the centre they should write the similarities of both diseases. At the end of the work we discuss and analyse every one's diagrams. Of course every our lesson follows by presentation to the topic. In our department there are a great numbers of multimedia presentations. Some of them are made by students. Clear presentations on themes Respiratory tract, Wellness and Health triangle, Jaundice, the Diseases of Liver and Bile Ducts and, many others are the main addition to our topics. Students learn the topic performed by teacher with great interest. They participate during group works actively. In some lessons we perform videos connected to topic. Using films in teaching process is effective also. In first year students by our curriculum we have a topic Journeys. After learning a unit we have a task – film

about Journeys. Students are fond of such kind of tasks. They watch a film and do several tasks according to it. This kind of occupation is very useful and interesting. Learners memorize the topic better and they are fully engaged. Of course it is a good way to pronounce English words correctly, because of listening native speaker's speech. They watch and comprehend given paragraph. Teaching language by the means of visual aids helps both teacher and students. Students take an active participation in the lesson. He/she are greatly interested in learning topic, do the tasks and comprehend the given material. As a conclusion we can add that using visual aids in teaching English is unalterable part of each ELT language.

CONCLUSION

Many of these issues may never be resolved but one thing that is sure is that the demand to learn languages and the use of new technologies in developing language learning materials will continue to increase. It will be interesting to see if the content of materials will become more authentic and if their activities will become more engaging. A blurb proclaims that the book offers rich opportunities for authentic communication but the units are restricted to the same old presentation / practice / production approach with the emphasis on controlled practice (Tomlinson et al. 2001; Masuhara et al. 2008). However I would like to celebrate many of the achievements made in materials development in the last 20 years, and I want to stress that

- experiential materials development courses in universities and teacher training institutions have not only led to more principled and effective materials, but they have increased the confidence, self-esteem, and professional competence of teachers too;
- the recent acceptance of materials development as an academic field of study has led to a massive increase in the number of graduate students researching the effectiveness of different types of materials (e.g., Tomlinson and Masuhara, 2010)
- the increase in academic research has been paralleled by an increase in publisher research (most of which is confidential and unpublished);
- publishers have continued to produce and promote excellent series of extensive readers to supplement their course books
- many institutions around the world have developed excellent in-house materials (Kanda University in Japan being an outstanding example of an institution which has developed a self-access learning centre from a principled mix of commercial and teacher made materials).

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